

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Optocouplers in space: SET templates (OptoSET)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA08-255
General application	<i>Space electronic equipment</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE: capture of SETs in optocoupler to define SET worst case waveforms</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>10/10/23; 07/11/23; 11/12/23; 21/02/24; 28/05/24</i>
Facility	<i>UCLouvain, CRC</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>20 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

Optocouplers are used in space systems to provide an efficient DC isolation between circuit functions with different references (ground).

The uncontrolled charge injection in a PN junction resulting from ionization coming from heavy ions can produce a self-recoverable false signal on the output of the optocoupler. These false signals are called Single Event Transients (SETs).

In the current ECSS Radiation Hardness Assurance, it is recommended to use a worst case SET waveform at the optocoupler output with a duration of 100 ns to simulate the SET and to analyse the impact on the electrical design. The use of worst-case waveforms makes it possible to avoid expensive heavy ions SEE tests. However, the radiation space community now wonders if this approach is still acceptable for optocouplers.

Thales Alenia Space has proposed to perform heavy ion tests on the most frequently used types of optocouplers in space applications: the phototransistor-based optocoupler, the photodiode-Darlington based optocoupler, the logic optocoupler, the fast (Schottky transistor output) optocoupler and the linear optocoupler.

The main objective of these heavy ions campaigns is to characterise the SET response of these optocouplers in various bias conditions. The outputs make it possible to define new worst-case waveforms and to develop, for a simple optocoupler (phototransistor), a simulation model that allows SET analysis in various electrical designs only by electrical simulation.

Experiment test report

A total of 5 campaigns were executed to collect enough data to define new worst-case waveforms.

As the primary goal is to capture the worst-case, irradiations were done with a LET higher than 60 MeV/mg/cm². At UCLouvain CRC, we use Xe ions (LET at surface 62.5 MeV/mg/cm²).

The tested references are the following: OLS249 (phototransistor); HCPL560 (Fast - Schottky transistor output); HCPL625 (logic optocoupler); HCPL675 (photodiode-Darlington); OLH7000 (linear).

Test setup

A “generic” test board has been designed. It makes it possible to easily change components around the optocoupler in a typical application. Strong care is taken to minimize the parasitic capacitance at the output of the DUT.

Generic Test board – Front view (Beam view)

Generic Test board – Back view

Dedicated active probes are designed with a low input capacitance and mechanically designed to be physically placed very close to the DUT (on the backside of the DUT). A trans-impedance amplifier is also designed with the objective of measuring the current sink without any influence of the parasitic components.

Per component type, a dedicated device board has been designed. Each device board can be inserted in the generic test board.

Active voltage probe (gain 1/10)

Test setup – Global view

Device opening

To have a direct view to the die (the receiver), it is mandatory to remove the platform with the IR LED and the silicone coating. Therefore, in order to be able to drive the receiver circuit, we have added a discrete external IR LED.

Device board with external IR LED

Device board. Side view

Single Event Effects likely to be observed

As the receiver is in a standard bipolar process, only SETs are expected to happen. Single Event Transient (SET) are parasitic pulses observable at the output of the device.

OLS249

Optocoupler OLS249 consists of a LED that is optically coupled to an N-P-N silicon phototransistor, which is mounted and coupled in a custom hermetic surface-mount technology (SMT) leadless chip carrier (LCC) package. It is one of the most used optocoupler in space equipment.

Forty runs were executed to characterize this device in various configurations. We made the test with different collector resistors, supply voltage and RC filter at the base of the phototransistor.

The waveform capture were done at the collector output in voltage mode with front-end amplifier:

Figure 1 - Front-end amplifier

Or with a trans-impedance amplifier.

Figure 2 - Trans-impedance amplifier

Observations

Here are some typical waveforms captured with our setup.

The red waveforms represent the signal at the output of the DUT. The cyan waveforms show the PPAC signal. This signal, coming from the cyclotron, displays a 100 ns pulse for each particle present in the beam. This signal allows to check the coherence of the SET with incoming particle and to detect double strike.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 5$ volts; $R_c = 1k$; $R_b = no$; $C_b = no$; LED OFF

Depending on the location of the strike on the die, we observe different time constants. We observe one slow time constant (around 16 μs) and a fast constant (around 100 ns).

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 5$ volts; $R_c = 100k$; $R_b = 1$ Meg; $C_b = no$; LED OFF

This second example, in another condition, shows (right waveform) a typical example of double strike. You can see the two blue pulses in perfect synchro with the SETs. This is a great advantage of having a particle detector covering the full beam.

Only the condition “LED OFF” exhibit pulses. With the LED ON, no SET were captured.

The next example shows a use-case with the trans-impedance amplifier. With this amplifier, we are able to capture the current pulled by the phototransistor with a very limited impact on the external circuitry. Without the influence of the parasitic capacitance, the response is strongly shorter in duration.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 12$ volts; $R_c = trans-impedance$ amplifier; $R_b = no$; $C_b = no$; LED OFF

Conclusions for OLS249 (optocoupler “Phototransistor” based)

SET to be considered:

- The amplitude of the SET observed does not go “rail to rails”,
- With $R_c < 10k$, the amplitude of the waveform is too small to trig a CMOS gate,
- SETs are only falling down (increase of the current pull down by the phototransistor),
- The SET waveforms show generally two time constants, a fast one and a slow one,
- The filter at the base ($R_b = 1Meg$, $C_b = 100pF$) is very efficient to remove the slow time constant (Ex : worst measured SET with $R_c = 100k$: - 2.9 Vpp; 7 μs but measured SET with $R_c = 1k$: - 1.6 Vpp; 90 ns),
- NB: The rise time of the waveform is directly linked to the value of the resistor at the collector.

HCPL560

Optocoupler HCPL560 is a single version. The channel contains a GaAsP light emitting diode that is optically coupled to an integrated high speed photon detector (10 Mbd typical). The output of the detector is an open collector Schottky clamped transistor. Internal shields provide a guaranteed common mode transient immunity specification of 1000 V/μs. For isolation voltage applications requiring up to 2500 Vdc. the polarity is inverting: LED ON => Output Low.

Test setup

It is the same generic setup that is used for all optocouplers.

Device opening

Device board with external IR LED

Device board. Side view

Observations

Here are some typical waveforms captured with our setup.

The red waveforms represent the signal at the output of the DUT. The cyan waveforms show the PPAC signal. This signal, coming from the cyclotron, displays a 100 ns pulse for each particle present in the beam. This signal allows to check the coherence of the SET with incoming particle and to detect double strike.

13 runs were executed to characterize this device.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 5$ volts; $R_c = 1k$; LED OFF => Output = High

Pulse SET (Worst-case: ~ 300 ns)

Graph of all waveforms

This optocoupler shows rail-to-rail SET with a total worst-case duration of 300 ns.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 5$ volts; $R_c = 1k$; LED ON => Output = Low

With the LED ON, this optocoupler shows positive going pulses. They have limited amplitude with high value of R_c but shows rail-to-rail SET with a $R_c=1\text{ kohms}$ and with a total worst-case duration of 500 ns. In some cases, this optocoupler shows a double pulse NOT due to a double strike (see PPAC waveform). It is probably coming from the use of the Schmitt trigger in the front-end circuitry.

Conclusions for HCPL 560 (optocoupler with open collector)

SET to be considered:

- The amplitude of the SET observed goes up to supply rails,
- SETs are present in both conditions (LED OFF or LED ON),
- With a R_c of 10 kohms, the maximum recorded pulse width is 700 ns.
- With a R_c of 100 kohms, the maximum recorded pulse width is 4 μ s.
- Higher resistors show higher pulse width.
- NB: The rise time of the waveform is directly linked to the value of the resistor at the collector.

HCPL625

This optocoupler is part of a family, manufactured by Avago, using the same die: HCPL-520x, HCPL-523x, HCPL-623x, HCPL-625x, 5962-88768 and 5962-88769. These devices are either single, dual or quad channel, hermetically sealed optocouplers. They are a logic gate optocoupler with the receiving die made in a bipolar process. Therefore, only SET are expected to happen.

HCPL625 is a quad version. Each channel contains an AlGaAs light emitting diode that is optically coupled to an integrated high gain photon detector. The detector has a threshold with hysteresis, which provides differential mode noise immunity and eliminates the potential for output signal chatter. The detector in the single-channel optocouplers has a tri-state output stage that allows for direct connection to data buses. The output is noninverting.

Test set-up

It is the same generic setup that is used for all optocouplers.

Device opening

Device board with external IR LED

Device board. Side view

Observations

Here are some typical waveforms captured with our setup.

The red waveforms represent the signal at the output of the DUT. The cyan waveforms show the PPAC signal. This signal, coming from the cyclotron, displays a 100 ns pulse for each particle present in the beam. This signal allows to check the coherence of the SET with incoming particle and to detect double strike.

13 runs were executed to characterize this device.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 5$ volts; LED ON => Output = High

Typical SET are rail-to-rail transients. Some small positive SET are also detected but have no impact on a digital signal.

 Single pulse SET (Worst-case: 1.3 μ s)

Double pulse example

Double pulses occur. Probably due to the hysteresis circuitry in the photodiode amplifier. It is sure that this phenomena is not due to a double strike by particles. The recording of the PPAC confirms this point.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 5$ volts; LED OFF => Output = Low

In this reverse state, the timing observed does not change.

Variation of the supply voltage don't significantly change the pulses duration.

Conclusions for HCPL625 (logic optocoupler)

SET to be considered:

- The amplitude of the SET observed goes up to supply rails,
- SETs are present in both conditions (LET ON or LED OFF),
- Double pulses are detected (probably due to the hysteresis circuitry),
- The maximum single pulse width is 1.3 μs.
- The maximum double pulses transient duration is 2.7 μs.

HCPL675

The tested optocoupler is part of a family, manufactured by Broadcom (Avago), using the same die: 6N140A, HCPL-675x, 83024, HCPL-570x, HCPL-177K, 5962-89810, HCPL-573x, HCPL-673x, 5962-89785, 5962-98002. These optocouplers are either single, dual or quad channel, hermetically sealed optocouplers. They are high gain optocouplers with the receiving die made in a bipolar process. Therefore, only SET are expected to happen.

HCPL675 is a quad version. Each channel contains a GaAsP light emitting diode that is optically coupled to an integrated high gain photon detector. The high gain output stage features an open collector output, providing both lower saturation voltage and higher signaling speed than what is typically possible with conventional photo-Darlington optocouplers.

Test set-up

It is the same generic setup that is used for all optocouplers.

Device opening

Device board with external IR LED

Device board. Side view

Observations

Here are some typical waveforms captured with our setup.

The red waveforms represent the signal at the output of the DUT. The cyan waveforms show the PPAC signal. This signal, coming from the cyclotron, displays a 100 ns pulse for each particle present in the beam. This signal allows to check the coherence of the SET with incoming particle and to detect double strike.

5 runs were executed to characterize this device.

Like the OLS249, only the condition “LED OFF” exhibits pulses. With the LED ON, no SET were observed.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 12$ volts; $R_c = 10k$; LED OFF => Output = High

In these conditions, rail-to-rail SET are captured. The longest one is around 600 ns and is a rare event. The second graph shows all waveforms captured. Only one capture goes rail-to-rail. All the other have a reduced amplitude. The recovery duration (rise time) is linked to the R_c resistor.

Pulse SET (Worst-case: ~ 600 ns)

Graph of all waveforms (124)

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 5$ volts; $R_c = 4k7$; LED OFF => Output = High.

In these conditions, rail-to-rail SET are captured. The longest one is around 500 ns and is a rare event. The second graph shows all waveforms captured. The worst-case event is rare and the other events are strongly reduced.

Pulse SET (Worst-case: 500 ns)

Graph of all waveforms (110)

Conclusions for HCPL675 (Optocoupler “Photo diode + Darlington” based)

SET to be considered:

- The amplitude of the SET observed goes up to supply rails,
- SETs are present only in the condition with the bipolar Darlington in linear mode (LET OFF),
- The maximum recorded pulse width is 600 ns ($R_c = 10K$, $V_s = 12V$).
- NB : The rise time of the waveform is directly linked to the value of the resistor at the collector and the supply voltage (the higher, the R_c , the higher the SET, the same holds for the supply voltage).

OLH7000

OLH7000 is a linear optocoupler manufactured by Skyworks (Isolink). This device consists of two IR LEDs in series, coupled to two PIN photodiode detectors.

During the typical use of OLH7000, the photodiode on the input side acts as a feedback device that allows an external feedback loop to ensure constant LED light output. A similar matching photodiode on the output side is used to drive an output circuit that is electrically isolated from the input.

Therefore, only SET are expected to happen.

Test set-up

It is the same generic setup that is used for all optocouplers.

Device opening

Device board with external IR LED

Device board. Side view

Bias conditions

The photodiode is biased in reverse mode by a supply voltage of 14 volts.
The LEDs are driven with a fixed current able to set a controlled current in the photodiode.

The following bias conditions were used:

LED: ON

V_{cc}: 14 volts

R_{load}: 100k or 10k or trans-impedance amplifier (~ 0 ohms)

V_{load}: 7 volts or 1 volts or ~ 0 volts

Voltage measurement with V-V amplifier

Current measurement with I-V amplifier

Observations

Here are some typical waveforms captured with our setup.

The red waveforms represent the signal at the output of the DUT. The cyan waveforms show the PPAC signal. This signal, coming from the cyclotron, displays a 100 ns pulse for each particle present in the beam. This signal allows to check the coherence of the SET with incoming particle and to detect double strike.

A total of 10 runs were executed to characterize this device.

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 14$ volts; $R_I = 100k$; LED ON => Output = 7 volts

Positive SET only. Due to current increase in the photodiode in reverse mode following the ion strike.

Pulse SET (Worst-case: ~ 3 μs)

Graph of all waveforms

Amplitude maximum: 2.26 volts; Duration maximum: ~3 μs

Bias conditions: $V_{cc} = 14$ volts; $R_I = 10k$; LED ON => Output = 1 volts

Positive SET only. Due to current increase in the photodiode in reverse mode following the ion strike.

Pulse SET (Worst-case: ~ 0.5 μs)

Graph of all waveforms

Amplitude maximum: 1.48 volts; Duration maximum: ~0.5 μs

Bias conditions: Current measurement in the photodiode via trans-impedance amplifier. $V_{cc} = 14$ volts

This measurement show the response of the photodiode (current and time) without any impact of the capacitance. The gain is 25 ohms.

Amplitude maximum negative pulse: 25 mV => 1 mA; Duration maximum: ~ 200 ns

Conclusions for the OLH7000:

- The SETs collected on the photodiode show the usual behaviour of a diode struck by an ion.
- The measurements done with the trans-impedance amplifier show the impact of the junction capacitance.
- The load resistor impact the time response.
- The test in application show the response coming from the primary and secondary photodiode.

OLS249 spice modelling

This paragraph summarises the activity carried out to find a relevant SPICE model that is representative of test results for the phototransistor OLS249 subjected to radiation of heavy ions. The model is based on existing phototransistor library models internal to TASI-B.

This work helped the understanding of physical event occurring under different radiation strike phenomena of OLS249. Outside the scope of this work is full characterization of the phototransistor, which would require additional measures on a relatively large amount of samples

This device consists of one IR LED optically coupled to a phototransistor.

Spice model representation (left), qualitative influence of device parameters in SET waveform (right)

Some parameters were adjusted in order to obtain representative waveforms for heavy ion strikes: The deposited charge, the BJT parameters: Cjc, Tf, Cje, IC, Bf, Cje, the BJT parameters with little influence: Is, Rb, the transmission line (RC) parameters as reverse biased Collector-Base junction: R,C,Len.

Adjusting the BJT spice model parameters provided good results for the majority of test cases under radiation.

Also, the transmission line model whose length represents the distance from the junction to the contacts provided good results that help better understand and model discrete devices behaviour under radiations.

The variables that are iterated in this simulations are the following:

- Rc: collector resistance (1k; 100k)
- Rbb: base to ground (1Meg, inf)
- Cbb: base to ground capacitor (0; 100pF)
- Vcc: Bias voltage (5V, 12V)

Here below a result for one test setup is illustrated. It is interpreted that the sharp peaks observed are due to a strike close to the contacts.

This result assumes a pre-charge of the junction b-e, this is an open point as it may be that previous HI strikes pre-charge this junction and have an effect on the level of the slow transient, but not on the peak. Peaks are representative with the smaller values of resistor but as the impedance is higher the peak is seen to decrease with respect to tests.

Simulations vs tests

Condition 1: $V_{cc}=5V$, $R_c = 1K$, $R_{bb}=\infty$, $C_{bb}=0$, LED OFF, Initial $V_{be} = 0.4V$

Condition 2: $V_{cc}=12V$, $R_c = 10K$, $R_{bb}=\infty$, $C_{bb}=0$, LED OFF, Initial $V_{be} = 0.4V$

Conclusions: The activity succeeded to interpret to a certain degree the complexity of heavy ion strikes in double junction devices. Transmission line length resolve well the presence or absence of peaks in the tests under HI. Spice model is considered representative enough as it represents well the behaviour of the device under different test conditions. The pre-charge of the b-e junction remains an open point, to be discussed if previous particles may be responsible of this pre-charge. A double-injection across the two junctions is a better candidate.

OLH7000 spice modelling

This paragraph summarises the activity carried out to find a relevant SPICE model that is representative of test results for the phototransistor OLH7000 subjected to radiation of heavy ions.

At the time of this activity, no previous model is found in our library.

This work helped the understanding of physical event occurring under different radiation strike phenomena of OLH7000.

The model is developed as a general model for a photodiode based optocoupler.

OLH7000 Spice model for SET

Therefore, there are different blocks to be modelled in SPICE:

- Charge injection current source
- RC transmission line as the L and G parameters are considered relatively low
- Parasitic elements of the photodiode receiver
- The active LED and current-to-current transmission block (CTR and rise/fall delays)

Simulations vs tests

Simulations are considered for reverse biased photodiode and resistance or trans-impedance amplifier in series.

Condition 1 : Photodiode with $RL = 100\text{ k}\Omega$

The LED is set to output different DC values at the load resistor.

The simulated dV/dt is slightly high, however we will see the next result gives a lower dV/dt than tests.

Condition 2: Photodiode with trans-impedance amplifier

RL is set to 1ohm and LED is OFF

One interesting result is the variation of the length of the transmission line to simulate the strike at different distances from the contacts of the device. Varying the length of the transmission line provides similar results compared to those found in the literature (Hooten, 2014), which confirms the assumptions that the junction could be modelled similarly to a RC transmission line.

Conclusions: SPICE model and test results are quite representative. Simulation of junction as a transmission line is regarded as sufficiently representative. Some additional work regarding adjusted values could provide more insights about the model such as the interpretation of R and C values in the junction transmission line.

Conclusions for TA08-255 project

This project gave us a great opportunity to explore the behaviours of SETs in various optocouplers. All these test campaigns made it possible to propose efficient worst-case waveforms to the ESA radiation working group and update ECSS-Q-ST-60-15C accordingly. The new revision of this ECSS is now enhanced with realistic worst-case waveforms. These campaigns also provided for designers a clear view of the “real” behaviour of the optocouplers used in Thales Alenia Space products and to improve the electrical modelling of these devices.

Thank you to RADNEXT for this important funding.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an ‘X’ next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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